

INVESTIGATION OF CNT FILTERING ACCORDING TO IN-PLANE AND OUT-OF-PLANE LCM INJECTION STRATEGIES

T. Grieser^{1*}, P. Mitschang¹

¹ Institut für Verbundwerkstoffe GmbH, Kaiserslautern, Germany

*Corresponding author (timo.grieser@ivw.uni-kl.de)

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1 Introduction

Innovative material synergies and composite processing strategies are the main topics of current ambitions to substitute metals through high performance composites. Besides the substitution of metals it is also possible to increase the lightweight potential of the composite applications while a reduction of manufacturing costs is present.

Carbon Nanotubes (CNTs) can improve the physical and mechanical properties of plastics with or without fiber reinforcement. Because of their high conductivity, it is possible to transfer electrical insulators to conductive components by processing CNTs doped resins. Thereby, conductive glass fiber reinforced polymer composites (GFRPC) could be utilized e.g. for cathaphoretic and antistatic coating or structural health monitoring. In the aerospace industry, modified carbon fiber reinforced polymer composites (CFRPC) could exhibit sufficient electrical conductivity for EMI shielding, de-icing or lightning strike protection.

The main challenge during the manufacturing of CNT doped laminates utilizing the common Resin Transfer Molding (RTM) process is the controlled distribution of the CNTs in the fiber structure. Despite their small size, filtering of the CNTs is likely during the impregnation of textile fiber structures, indifferent which in-plane injection strategy (ring or center gate) is used [1]. In the past, two different types of filtering have been described: Cake filtration and deep bed filtration [2, 3].

Rieber et al. report about generally decreasing electrical conductivity with increasing distance from the inlet and lower volume conductivity inside a fiber yarn due to the filtering of CNTs by RTM produced laminates [1]. Fan and Qiu give a deeper insight to this problem and suggest adaptations of the process strategy [4, 5]. The degree of filtering is also strongly related on the quality of dispersion of

the CNTs in the resin before impregnation [6, 7] and the type of the textile. The appearance of unwanted agglomerates enormously affects the critical percolation threshold for doped epoxy resins [8]. Therefore, a good dispersion of CNTs is required. Furthermore, the percolation threshold is strongly dependent on the matrix system which will be used as carrier of the filler [2, 8]. Limitations of the maximum CNT content exist for each matrix system and must not be exceeded [9]. The curing can also impact the state of dispersion, which can lead to unwanted realignment and agglomeration of the CNTs [10]. Further implementation strategies exist, e.g. modifications of the fiber structure itself before impregnation. These are not considered within this study.

Nevertheless, innovative processing strategies are required to solve the filtering problem during the manufacturing of FRPC laminates.

Previous studies already showed that the degree of filtering is too high for a central inlet injection strategy. Different kinds of fillers as well as resin and fiber structures were utilized in the previous research. Filtering was present for all specifications. The comparative GFRPC and CFRPC laminates were manufactured using a RTM process with a ring inlet as in-plane injection strategy (see Fig. 1). [1]

This study investigates filtering effects according to out-of-plane injection strategies via Advanced RTM. The CNT contents in the epoxy resin varied between 0.15 – 1.15 wt.-%. Different set-ups of electrical conductivity measurements (volume, surface, and through the thickness) were carried out. Furthermore, electrical conductivity topographies of the entire laminates were generated to investigate the distribution of CNTs in a larger scale. The main question of this thesis was if it would be possible to control the CNT filtering according to improved injection strategies? The results were compared to

in-plane injection strategies via RTM of the previous studies.

2 Research approach

The Advanced RTM process, which is a modified RTM process, can overcome the obstacles during the injection phase in order to prevent filtering of CNTs. Fig. 2 exemplarily shows the Advanced RTM process. The global manufacturing procedure, starting with cutting and stacking of the textiles and draping of the stack to generate the preform, is the same as for standard RTM. But during the injection phase the mold is not completely closed. A gap between the upper mold and the fiber structure remains and the CNT doped resin is able to distribute over the complete surface. Subsequently, the actual impregnation takes place through the closing of the mold whereby the filled resin impregnates the textile stack through the thickness. At the end of the injection (mold completely closed) the final fiber volume content is reached. By using this technology the impregnation length is enormously shortened to the thickness of the part which commonly varies between 1 and 5 mm. Regarding the RTM process the impregnation length is many times shorter and independent on the dimension of the part. The enormous reduction of impregnation length via Advanced RTM should prevent or at least minimize the filtering of CNTs to reach the goal of a homogeneous distribution of this filler.

3 Materials and test methods

In this study the aerospace certified two component epoxy system HexFlow® RTM6-2 was utilized. The service temperatures are between -60 °C and 180 °C. It is the transportable version of the standard HexFlow® RTM6 with a high glass transition temperature. The CNTs were of the type NC7000 from NANOCYL™. These thin multi-wall CNTs have an average diameter of 9.5 nm and an average length of 1.5 mm, which result in a high aspect ratio >150. Master batches with specific amounts of CNTs were manufactured by Nanocyl to ensure a good dispersion. The carbon fiber material was a standard textile from Hexcel, Hexply G0986. It is a twill 2/2 woven fabric (HTA 5131 6K) with a nominal weight of 300 g/m² containing 2.5 wt.-% epoxy powder on both sides. The nominal

construction is 3.5 yarns/cm (weft and warp direction) with a ply thickness of 0.29 mm. The utilized glass fiber fabric was the standard textile 1265 from Hexcel. It is a plain woven fabric with a nominal area weight of 390 g/m² and 5.9 yarns/cm in warp and 6.6 yarns/cm in weft direction.

3.1 Viscosity tests

First of all, the viscosity of neat RTM6 Part A and RTM6 (containing different amounts of CNTs) was examined. The utilized viscometer was a Brookfield DV-II + Pro, the spindle name was LV #1, and the rotating speed (0.5 – 30 rpm) was adjusted to the changing temperature of the resin which varied between 80 °C and 120 °C. The filling quantity of CNTs for the doped resins was 0.1, 0.15, 0.2 and 0.3 wt.-%. After scaling down the batches from Nanocyl to achieve the individual CNT amounts, all samples were mixed for 30 minutes at 90 °C and 180 rpm. The mixing method was automatically using an overhead stirrer. Also a vacuum of 5 mbar was applied during mixing.

3.2 Manufacturing of CNT doped resin plates

CNT doped RTM6-2 resin plates were manufactured to determine the percolation threshold of the material synergy. The utilized curing cycle is displayed in Fig. 3. For these plates the CNT filling quantities were 0.06, 0.07, 0.08, 0.1, 0.13, 0.15, and 0.2 wt.-%. The dimension of the plates was 110x110x3 mm each, manufactured via RTM utilizing a pressure tank for the injection. Also a vacuum of 0.5 mbar was applied before injection. The empirical findings of the viscosity tests and the manufacturing of the doped resin plates were utilized to process GFRPC and CFRPC laminates.

3.3 Manufacturing CNT-doped GFRPC and CFRPC laminates via Advanced RTM

The final cavity of the mold, which was used for both processes, was 570x470x3 mm. A silicon layer was placed in the mold as sealing and to realize a laminate size of 300x300x3 mm. 10 layers of the woven glass textile resulted in a fiber volume fraction of 51.5 % and 10 layers of the carbon fabric resulted in a fiber volume fraction of 56.1 %. Previous tests showed that both fabrics contain almost the same permeability values at the

mentioned fiber volume fractions. Therefore, the glass material functioned as CNT indicator and was a very good reference to the G0986 in order to evaluate the CNT filtering. The CNT filling quantity of the doped resin was 0.15, 0.5, and 1.15 wt.-% for the CFRPC laminates and 0.15 and 1.15 wt.-% for the GFRPC laminates. The samples were mixed for 30 minutes at 90 °C and 180 rpm to achieve the individual CNT quantity using an overhead stirrer. Also a vacuum of 0.5 mbar was applied during mixing to ensure a proper evacuation.

For the Advanced RTM laminates a kind of central injection strategy was utilized. Therefore, the CNT doped resin was injected in the slightly opened mold (1/6 mm) on top of the upper layer. According to the slightly opened mold (see Fig. 4), the fiber volume content decreased from 56.1 % to 46.9 % (for CFRPC). After the CNT doped resin was completely distributed all over the surface, the final cavity height of 3 mm was set. The impregnation of the material through the thickness proceeded and the intended fiber volume content of 56.1 % was reached. The curing cycle was the same as for the neat resin plates.

3.4 Electrical conductivity test set-ups: Through the thickness, volume, and surface conductivity

The resistances of the different types of materials were measured utilizing a Keithley 2601 A System Sourcemeter. Crocodile clamps, test probes, and flat electrodes were used as current input tools. Furthermore, the conductive silver Silver DAG 1415 from PLANO GmbH was applied to the samples as contact medium.

The distribution of the CNTs through the thickness of the entire laminates could be examined by electrical conductivity topographies. A grid of contacting points was applied on both surfaces of the laminate (see Fig. 6). The measurements were performed according to DIN IEC 60093 (VDE 0303 part 30): 1993 [11]. The applied potential U varied between 3 – 30 V according to the type of fibers (carbon respectively glass). The current I was kept constant at 1 A. The electrical conductivity was determined as follows

$$\sigma = \frac{1}{R} \cdot \frac{t}{A} = \frac{I}{U} \cdot \frac{4t}{\pi d^2} \quad (1)$$

where R is the electrical resistance, t the laminate thickness, A the contact area, and d the diameter of the contact point. Origin 8 was used as analyzing and viewer program to generate the topographies.

After the testing of the entire laminates was completed, the samples were cut into shape for volume, surface, and additional through the thickness conductivity measurements. For these tests a self-build test device, displayed in Fig.5, and the Keithley 2601 Sourcemeter were utilized.

The volume and surface conductivity tests referred to DIN EN ISO 3915:1999 [12]. The applied potential U varied between 3 mV and 3 V according to the type of fiber. The current I was kept constant at 1 A. The length of the samples varied between 20 and 150 mm, the width was 10 mm, and the thickness 3 mm for each sample. Initial tests showed that there was no difference in the resultant electrical conductivities in 0° and 90° fiber orientation of the used materials. Therefore, the results presented here are limited to the 0° orientation of the samples. The conductive silver was applied on the fronts of the samples for the measurements in volume (see Fig. 7). The computation of the volume conductivity was done by the following formula

$$\sigma = \frac{1}{R} \cdot \frac{t}{A} = \frac{I}{U} \cdot \frac{l}{b \cdot d} \quad (2)$$

where l is the length, b the width, and d the thickness of the sample.

Two parallel lines were suited on the top and on the bottom of each sample to measure the surface conductivity on both sides. The distance between the two lines on one side was $t = 10$ mm to achieve a squared testing area (see Fig. 8). An Excel-based software tool was used as analyzing and viewer program for both test set-ups.

The detailed investigation of the through the thickness conductivity and thus the filtering of CNTs was performed with the GFRPC samples. The samples surfaces were milled five times (totally) by losing 0.4 – 0.5 mm thickness by each step. An electronic router from Metabo OFE 738 was height-adjustable applied on a linear guidance (see Fig. 9). After each milling step the prepared sample surfaces were contacted with conductive silver and tested through the thickness utilizing the Keithley 2601 Sourcemeter. The schematic test set-up is displayed

in Fig. 10. The measurements were performed according to DIN IEC 60093 (VDE 0303 part 30): 1993 [11]. The applied potential U was 5 V and the current I was kept constant at 1 A.

Also effects of changing boundary conditions for through the thickness measurements were investigated. The size of measuring points and the offset of opposite measuring points were changed and optimized.

4 Results

4.1 Viscosity change according to the implementation of CNTs

The implementation of CNTs into a matrix system enormously changes the injection behavior of liquid composite molding processes. Therefore, it is essential to perform viscosity tests before the manufacturing of the Advanced RTM laminates. Different filling amounts of CNTs in the epoxy system were investigated to make an assessment about critical CNT content vs. injectability.

No difference was measured for evacuated and not evacuated neat RTM6-2 Part A (see Fig. 11). Starting with increasing the CNT content to 0.15 wt.-%, the viscosity increased, but only slightly. In contrast, a pronounced slope was measured by adding 0.2 wt.-% CNT to the matrix. By adding 0.3 wt.-%, the viscosity reached a very high level of nearly 2500 mPas at 80°C compared to <700 mPas for the 0.15 wt.-% CNT resin. At higher temperatures (between 110 and 120°C) the viscosities were below 500 mPas except of the 0.3 wt.-% filled configuration. Consequently, 0.3 wt.-% CNT is most probably critical for the injection according to the high viscosity. Viscosities below 500 mPas are generally uncritical for the injection process, which means that up to 0.2 wt.-% it should be less critical, but filtering can still be present.

4.2 Volume conductivity

According to the basic physical properties of thermoset matrix systems, glass fibers, and carbon fibers, it is obvious that the resultant electrical conductivities are not at the same level.

The natural insulation epoxy matrix could be turned into a semiconductor according to the implementation of CNTs. Up to a filling amount of 0.09 wt.-% the material combination was an

insulator. At the filling amount of 0.1 wt.-% an average electrical conductivity of $3.8E-08$ S/m was measured the first time. Increasing the CNT amount up to 0.15 wt.-% resulted in a pronounced increase (four decades) of electrical conductivity up to $1.5E-04$ S/m, which only slightly increased for filling contents over 0.2 wt.-%. For 0.2 wt.-% CNTs the resultant average electrical conductivity in volume achieved $2.3E-04$ S/m. The percolation threshold for the RTM6-2 / NC7000 material combination is consequently located between 0.09 – 0.15 wt.-% CNTs (see Fig. 12).

Introducing the CNT doped resins into the glass fiber structures, the resulting electrical conductivity in volume is further increased (see Fig. 13).

Compared to the volume conductivity of $1.49E-04$ S/m for the 0.15 wt.-% CNT doped resin plates, an average conductivity of $1.13E-02$ S/m measured for the GFRPC laminate containing the same amount of CNTs was measured. The rise in conductivity ranged about two decades. This is caused by a closer network of CNTs. By adding 1.15 wt.-% CNT into the GFRPC laminate a resultant conductivity of $1.11E01$ S/m was measured. It seems that CNT agglomerations emerge while the doped resin flows through the fiber structure. This is most probably the reason for this effect. The agglomerations mainly emerge in front of the “gaps”, through which the CNTs could pass according to their small size if not agglomerated. The so called cake filtering appears dealing with the highly doped resin, which results in CNT-rich areas on top of the surfaces. This is also described by other researchers [1, 2, 3]. Subsequently, it is imaginable that for the highly doped GFRPC laminates the conductive paths are only on the top surfaces of the laminate, whereby the 0.15 wt.-% filled composite most probably exhibits more paths through the entire volume. Nevertheless, the materials are still semiconductors. The analysis of CNT filtering will be described in detail in the next paragraphs by the investigation of the through the thickness conductivities of the entire laminates.

Regarding to the CFRPC laminates the electrical conductivities in volume were about three decades higher compared to the GFRPC laminates, due to the conductive properties of carbon fibers. The average conductivity for the CFRPC-reference was at the same level as for the CNT doped laminates. Only slightly differences were measured which can be

seen in Fig. 13. The conductivities varied between $1.07E04$ S/m for the CFRPC reference (without CNTs) and $2.11E04$ S/m for the 0.50 wt.-% CFRPC configuration. This means, that for volume conductivity measurements of CFRPC laminates the carbon fibers still have the dominant part and the presence of CNTs can be neglected in terms of volume conductivity.

4.3 Surface conductivity

According to the previously mentioned percolation threshold of the CNT doped neat resin plates (see Fig. 12) not all plates without fibers could be tested for surface conductivity. The first measureable averaged surface conductivity was recorded for the 0.13 wt.-% CNT configuration with an average of $1.22E-08$ S. The maximum of $2.52E-07$ S was found for the 0.2 wt.-% CNT doped resin plate. No difference was measured due to top or bottom surface of the samples.

Increased surface conductivities were measured for the fiber reinforced laminates (see Fig. 14). The surface conductivity of the GFRPC laminates differed between top and bottom surface. The 0.15 wt.-% laminate achieved a surface conductivity of $2.04E-05$ S on top compared to $4.19E-06$ S on the bottom surface. The surface conductivity of the highly filled GFRPC laminate reached $9.94E-03$ S on the top surface, but no conductivity was measured on the bottom. This suits the findings of the volume conductivity measurements, which means that filtering is present through the thickness of the laminates for the highly filled GFRPC laminate. Only slightly changes were measured for the 0.15 wt.-% CNT GFRPC laminate.

For the CFRPC laminates the surface conductivities varied between $2.29E-01$ (CF reference) and $7.26E-01$ S (1.15 wt.-% CNT) for the top surfaces and between $1.68E-01$ (0.15 wt.-% CNT) - $4.53E-01$ S (1.15 wt.-% CNT) for the bottom surfaces. Thus, the conductivity was two decades higher compared to the GFRPC laminates. Difference between the top and bottom surfaces could be measured. In some cases e.g. for the 0.15wt.-% and 1.15 wt.-% configurations the surface conductivities on top were higher, but this trend could not be ensured for the 0.5 wt.-% CNT CFRPC laminate. All in all, the surface conductivities for CFRPC laminates were located at almost the same level.

4.4 Through the thickness conductivity

The evaluation of the through the thickness conductivities was focused on the FRPC laminates since obviously no filtering is present at the neat resin plates.

In Fig. 15 the filtration of CNT through the fibers is shown. Strong backlight was utilized to visualize this effect. The analysis of the through the thickness conductivity was performed with the topographies based on the data of the measurements of the applied conductive grid (see Fig. 15 left image). The through the thickness conductivities of the displayed 300×300 mm² GFRPC laminate containing 0.15 wt.-% CNTs alternate between $8.50E-10$ and $2.6E-02$ S/m. The CNT distribution all over the laminate was almost evenly, but filtering through the thickness was still given at some locations. The lacks of conductivity can be related to the absence of conductive paths (through the thickness). Slightly increasing the CNT amount for the doped resin could solve this appearance.

No through the thickness conductivity could be measured for the highly filled GFRPC laminate. Therefore, further analysis was required to investigate the filtering of the CNTs. The laminates were cut into small slices and turned about 90° to view the cross-sections. Fig. 16 displays this: (A) displays the entire 0.15 wt.-% doped GFRPC laminate, (B) the orientation of the cut slices, (C) the 1.15 wt.-% doped GFRPC laminate slices, and (D) the 0.15 wt.-% slices. The numbers 1 - 9 correspond to the increasing distance from the center of the laminates. The right image (D) clearly shows that the CNTs passed the entire thickness of the laminate according to the out-of-plane injection strategy. In this case, the CNT content of 0.15 wt.-% was on the one side high enough to generate electrical conductive paths and on the other side low enough to minimize the filtering of the CNTs through the thickness. Nevertheless, the CNTs were not able to be located inside the yarns. Only in the gaps between the yarns CNTs were present. Regarding the 1.15 wt.-% CNT doped GFRPC laminate (C) the through the thickness conductivity could not be determined. The filtering of the CNTs through the thickness was too high in this case. The CNTs could not pass the entire thickness of the laminate. Only the first three plies could be impregnated, which

means that no conductive path was given. Cake filtering was present.

Also topographies of the CFRPC laminates were performed with the result that no obvious improvement was measured for the 0.15 wt.-% laminate compared to the reference. Fig. 17 displays the topography of 1.15 wt.-% CFRPC laminate and the laminate itself. The CNTs on top of the surface can be clearly seen and the presence of CNTs results in higher electrical through the thickness conductivities. The absence of CNTs in the boundary areas of the laminate is attributed to the manufacturing procedure. This can be solved with increasing injection time before closing the mold via the Advanced RTM process.

Besides the detailed investigation of the through the thickness conductivity according to the visual inspection of the GFRPC cross-sections, also measurements with decreasing laminate thicknesses (stepwise) were performed as described in chapter 3. The thickness reduction was performed from the bottom surface to the top surface based on the assumption that CNT rich areas were located on top of the laminates (higher conductive zones) and lower conductive zones were located on the bottom of the samples. Regarding the 0.15 wt.-% CNT doped GFRPC laminate the specific through the thickness conductivity remains at almost one level while decreasing the sample thickness. The conductivity varied within a range of $2.96E-04$ to $8.00E-04$ S/m. This underlines the findings of the visual inspections that almost no filtering occurred.

Quite the contrary was measured for the 1.15 wt.-% doped GFRPC laminate. No through the thickness conductivity was measured up to a sample thickness of 1.5 mm ($\sigma < 1E-10$). For the sample thickness of 1.2 mm the conductivity was in the range of $7.4E-08$ – $9.8E-08$ S/m, which is still lower compared to the 0.15 wt.-% GFRPC laminate. Only for laminate thicknesses below 0.6 mm higher conductivities between $3.79E-01$ - $1.33E00$ were measured.

5 Discussions

The main task of this study was to minimize or rather control the filtering of CNTs according to the out-of-plane injection strategy. In comparison to the common RTM process where filtering is absolutely present, it was possible to influence the CNT filtering according to the improved injection

strategy. An optimized CNT content has led to almost filtering-free FRPC laminates. Therefore, it is reasonable to further investigate and optimize injection strategies to control the filtering of CNTs. No remarkable improvement of volume conductivity could be observed for the CFRPC laminates according to the dominance of the carbon fibers. The second task of this study was to find adequate analyzing tools to investigate the filtering through the thickness. Two inspection methods were utilized and successfully proofed.

6 Conclusions

The main target of the study was the investigation of CNT filtering on surface, volume, and through the thickness conductivity by utilizing an out-of-plane injection strategy. Therefore, CNT doped resin plates, GFRPC and CFRPC laminates containing different amounts of CNTs from 0.15 to 1.15 wt.-% were manufactured by the Advanced RTM process. These laminates were examined according to the different types of conductivity. The findings are:

- CNTs are able to turn insulative material into semiconductors (doped resin plates) and percolation threshold was identified
- Higher conductivities are generated for GFRPC laminates compared to neat resin plates while containing the same amount of CNTs
- Presence of CNTs can be neglected in terms of volume conductivity of CFRPC laminates
- Homogeneously distribution of CNTs could be achieved according to the out-of-plane injection strategy
- Adequate methods to investigate the through the thickness conductivity were successfully generated

The results have shown that out-of-plane injection strategies are able to handle filtering problems. Certainly an optimized CNT content is absolutely important to generate conductive paths and to keep the formation of agglomerations of CNT at a low level. Further investigation of the filtering of CNTs in combination with improved injection strategies are required to control the filtering for specific applications. For instance, targeted and designed filtering could be utilized for the generation of highly conductive surfaces which function as e.g. lightning strike protection.

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Fig. 1. Ring inlet as in-plane injection strategy for RTM process

Fig. 2. Schematic procedure of the Advanced RTM process

Fig. 3. RTM6-2 curing cycle for CNT doped resin plates and fiber reinforced CFRPC and GFRPC laminates

Fig. 4. Central inlet as out-of-plane injection strategy for the Advanced RTM process

Fig.5. Test device for volume, surface and through the thickness conductivity measurements

Fig. 6. Test set-up for through the thickness conductivity of entire laminates

Fig. 7. Test set-up for in-plane volume conductivity

Fig. 8. Test set-up for in-plane surface conductivity

Fig. 9. Milling device to stepwise reduce the thickness of the samples in z-direction

Fig. 10. Test set-up for through the thickness conductivity measurements of milled samples

Fig. 11. Viscosity progressions of RTM6-2 Part A doped CNT systems according to different filling amounts (neat resin, 0.15, 0.2, 0.3 wt.-%) and the temperature

Fig. 12. Percolation threshold of RTM6-2 doped with different CNT amounts

Fig. 13. Overview of volume conductivity of CNT doped neat epoxy resin (0.15wt.-%), GFRPC (0.15 and 1.15 wt.-% CNT) and CFRPC (reference, 0.15, 0.5, and 1.15 wt.-% CNT) laminates

Fig. 14. Overview of surface conductivities (top and bottom surfaces) of the CNT doped GFRPC and CFRPC laminates

Fig. 15. Topography of through the thickness conductivity of the 0.15 wt.-% CNT GFRPC laminate (left); Image of GFRPC laminate (containing a grid of conductive points) performed with strong backlight

Fig. 16. CNT doped GFRPC laminate with grid of measuring points manufactured by Advanced RTM containing 0.15 wt.-% (A, B and D); CNT doped GFRPC laminate containing 1 wt.-% CNTs (C)

Fig. 17. Topography of through the thickness conductivity of the 1.15 wt.-% CNT GFRPC laminate (left); Image of GFRPC laminate (right)

Fig. 18. Through the thickness conductivity of the CNT doped GFRPC laminates according to decreasing sample thickness

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